

MEDICAL SCIENCES

COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE LEVEL OF CAUSES OF MORTALITY OF THE POPULATION IN AZERBAIJAN BEFORE, DURING AND AFTER THE COVID - 19 PANDEMIC

Isgandarova S.

*Azerbaijan State Institute for Advanced Medical Studies named after A. Aliyev
Baku, Azerbaijan*

ABSTRACT

Research Objective: To comparatively assess the levels and causes of population mortality in Azerbaijan before, during, and after the COVID-19 pandemic.

Materials and Methods: The study used official state statistics from 2018 to 2023 (two years before, two years during, and two years after the pandemic). The average annual number of deaths was calculated for the periods 2018–2019, 2020–2021, and 2022–2023, along with the average annual mortality rate per 1,000 population. To neutralize the effect of age as a factor, standardized mortality rates were calculated using the direct standardization method.

Results: During the two years prior to the pandemic and the second year after it, mortality from infectious and parasitic diseases (including viral infections) did not differ significantly (0,077; 0,067; and 0,077‰ respectively). In the first and second years of the pandemic, mortality rates increased by 7.6, 8.6, and 2.4 times respectively compared to 2018 (0,587; 0,665; and 0,288‰). The average annual excess mortality during and after the pandemic was 0,554‰ and 0,0605‰, respectively.

Before the pandemic, mortality from circulatory system diseases (3,453 and 3,270‰) showed a decreasing trend. During the pandemic, this rate significantly increased (4,123 and 4,152‰), and after the pandemic, it dropped back to pre-pandemic levels (0,269 and 0,224‰). The average annual excess mortality from circulatory system diseases during the pandemic was 0,776‰, which exceeded the excess mortality from infectious diseases (0,554‰).

Conclusion: In Azerbaijan, the pre-pandemic annual mortality rate was 5,7‰ (standardized rate: 8,5‰), with leading causes being circulatory system diseases (3,361‰), neoplasms (0,888‰), external influences (0,281‰) and digestive system diseases (0,268‰). During the pandemic, mortality increased from 5,7‰ to 7,65‰ (excess mortality of 1,95‰), primarily due to excess deaths from infectious diseases (COVID-19) (0,554‰), circulatory system diseases (0,776‰), respiratory diseases (0,176‰), external causes (0,17‰), neoplasms (0,095‰), nervous system diseases (0,077‰), and symptoms, syndromes, and ill-defined conditions (0,12‰). After the pandemic, the average annual mortality rate remained high at 5,95‰ compared to the pre-pandemic period, with an excess mortality of 0,25‰ (0,221‰ from symptoms, syndromes, and ill-defined conditions; 0,0605‰ from infectious diseases; 0,0195‰ from external causes; 0,01‰ from neoplasms).

Keywords: cause of death, COVID-19, pandemic, comparative assessment, level.

Introduction. The consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic are being studied in many countries around the world. Particular attention is paid to the size of excess mortality associated with the pandemic [1-3]. The focus of scientists is on the analysis of morbidity and mortality of the population during the pandemic [4], the sex and age structure of mortality from COVID-19, changes in the structure of causes of death [5-8] and various aspects of regional monitoring [9,10]. There are publications on the results of summarizing data from countries of the world on mortality during the pandemic [11-13]. Some studies provide an estimate of excess mortality based on national statistics from the USA [14-16], San Paulo [17], and Spain [15,18]. These studies draw attention to the need to accurately measure the consequences of the pandemic, which is important for an objective assessment of the role of health services in each country. It is regrettable that documentation of deaths due to COVID-19 is not always complete, for various reasons (insufficient availability of full examination of patients, difficulty in determining the role of COVID-19 in cases of deaths from diseases of the circulatory system, cancer and other pathologies with a positive test for COVID-19). Therefore, the true impact

of COVID-19 can be assessed by comparing the trend and mortality rate before, during and after the pandemic [4,12].

Purpose of the study. Comparatively assess the levels of causes of population mortality in Azerbaijan before, during and after a Pandemic COVID - 19.

Materials and research methods. The materials of state statistics for 2018-2023 (two years before, two years during and two years after the pandemic) were used.

The average annual number of deaths were determined for 2018-2019, 2020-2021 and 2022-2023, and the average annual mortality rate per 1000 population was calculated accordingly. To level out the role of the age factor, standardized mortality rates were additionally calculated using the direct standardization method. The difference between the average annual mortality rates during and before the pandemic was considered as the excess mortality rate during the pandemic. A similar method was used to determine the excess mortality rate after the pandemic.

The results obtained. The results of the study are presented in the table. Within two years before the pandemic and until the second year after the pandemic, the

mortality rate of the population due to infectious and parasitic diseases (including virus infections) did not noticeably differ from each other (0,077; 0,067 and 0,077‰). In the first and second years after the pandemic, the mortality rate increased by 7,6; 8,6 and 2,4 times, respectively, compared to 2018 (0,587; 0,665 and 0,288‰). The level of average annual excess mortality during the pandemic and after a pandemic was 0,554 and 0,0605‰, respectively.

The mortality rate due to the diseases of the endocrine system for 2018-2019 was similar (0,159 and 0,151‰), in the first year of the pandemic it increased to 0,201‰, and in the second year it decreased to 0,169‰, after the pandemic the mortality rate was lower than before the pandemic (0,119 and 0,124‰). Excessive mortality during the pandemic was 0,03‰.

The mortality rate due to diseases of the nervous system before the pandemic (0,086; 0,085‰) and in the first year of the pandemic (0,074‰) practically did not change and in the following years increased more than 3 times (0,251; 0,243 and 0,211‰). Excessive annual death rate after the pandemic (0,1415 ‰) was more than during the pandemic (0,77 ‰).

Before the pandemic, the mortality rate due to diseases of the circulatory system (3,453 and 3,270‰) had a decline trend, over the years of the pandemic increased markedly (4,123 and 4,152‰), and after a pandemic decreased to the level of the pre-pandemic (0,265 and 0,224‰).

The average annual level of excess mortality during a pandemic due to diseases of the circulatory sys-

tem was 0,776‰ and was greater than the level of average annual excessive mortality due to infectious diseases (0,554‰).

The mortality rate due to respiratory diseases was stable before the pandemic (0,186 and 0,187‰), increased during the pandemic (0,315 and 0,410‰), and after the pandemic became lower than the pre-pandemic level (0,127 and 0,135‰). Excessive annual mortality during a pandemic was 0,176‰.

The mortality rate due to diseases of the digestive system before the pandemic (0,266 and 0,271‰), during the pandemic (0,252 and 0,265‰) and after the pandemic (0,217 and 0,268‰) changed chaotically, the average annual indicator had a downward trend (0,268; 0,258 and 0,220‰) in a years before, during and after a pandemic. There was no excessive mortality during the pandemic period. A similar trend was characteristic of deaths due to diseases of the genitourinary system, individual states arising in the perinatal period and congenital anomalies.

In Azerbaijan, due to the insufficient availability of high-quality medical care, mortality due to inaccurately diagnosed pathologies is relatively high. Therefore, symptoms and signs of disease are often indicated as immediate and initial causes. In 2018, 2019 and 2020, the mortality rate due to the above causes was similar (0,163; 0,170; 0,162‰). In 2021 and after the pandemic, mortality due to the above causes increased more than 2 times (0,411; 0,471; 0,344‰). Excess average annual mortality, for which the "symptom" was indicated as the cause, after the pandemic (0,221) was up to 2 times higher than during the pandemic (0,120‰).

Table.

Dynamics of the mortality rate of the population of Azerbaijan (%) in 2018-2023, the size of excess mortality during and after the pandemic.

Cause of mortality	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Average annual		Excess mortality		
							2018-2019	2020-2021	2022-2023	2020-2021	2022-2023
Some infectious and parasitic diseases	0,077	0,067	0,587	0,665	0,188	0,077	0,072	0,626	0,132	0,554	0,0605
Neoplasms	0,888	0,888	0,988	0,847	0,829	0,967	0,888	0,917	0,898	0,095	0,01
Endocrine diseases, nutritional disorders and metabolic disorders substances	0,159	0,151	0,201	0,169	0,119	0,124	0,155	0,185	0,121	0,03	-0,033
Diseases of the nervous system	0,086	0,085	0,074	0,251	0,243	0,211	0,085	0,162	0,227	0,077	0,1415
Diseases of the system circulatory	3,453	3,27	4,123	4,152	3,41	3,268	3,361	4,137	3,339	0,776	-0,022
Respiratory diseases	0,186	0,187	0,315	0,41	0,127	0,135	0,186	0,362	0,131	0,176	-0,055
Diseases of organs digestion	0,266	0,271	0,252	0,265	0,224	0,217	0,168	0,258	0,220	-0,01	-0,048
Urogenital system diseases	0,127	0,127	0,132	0,124	0,103	0,111	0,127	0,128	0,107	0,001	-0,02
Congenital anomalies	0,102	0,101	0,093	0,035	0,039	0,127	0,101	0,064	0,083	-0,0375	-0,0185
Symptoms, signs and ill-defined conditions	0,021	0,02	0,021	0,018	0,013	0,017	0,020	0,019	0,015	-0,001	-0,0055
Injuries, poisoning and some other consequences of exposure to external causes	0,163	0,17	0,162	0,411	0,431	0,344	0,166	0,286	0,387	0,12	0,221
Congenital anomalies	0,282	0,281	0,606	0,298	0,289	0,313	0,281	0,452	0,170	0,1705	0,0195
Actual	5,81	5,618	7,554	7,645	6,015	5,911	5,7	7,65	5,95	1,95	0,25
Standardized	8,60	8,41	11,11	11,46	9,15	9,16	8,50	11,28	9,16	2,72	0,66

The mortality rate due to injuries and poisoning for 2018, 2019, 2021, 2022 and 2023 was similar (0,282; 0,281; 0,298; 0,289; 0,313 and 0,281‰). Only in 2020, when the war in Karabakh began and ended in the country, did this become the cause of death due to injuries (0,606‰).

The overall mortality rate of the population in Azerbaijan was relatively stable before the pandemic (5,810 and 5,618‰). During the pandemic, the indicator increased significantly (7,554 and 7,645‰), which after the pandemic decreased to the level of 2018-2019 (6,015 and 5,911‰). The excess average annual mortality rate was 1,95‰ during the pandemic and 0,25‰ after the pandemic. To level out the role of age factor in changes in mortality rates over a six-year period, the standardized mortality rate was calculated. The level of standardized mortality rate in Azerbaijan for 2018 and 2019 was almost the same (8,60 and 8,41‰). The indicator was higher during the pandemic (11,11 and 11,46‰) and after the pandemic (9,15 and 9,16‰). Excessive average annual standardized mortality rate was 2,72 ‰ during and 0,66‰ after the pandemic.

Discussion of the results obtained. In the Russian Federation, mortality in 2020 compared with 2019 increased by 18,9% [4]. In Azerbaijan, the increase in mortality in 2020 was 34,4%. An increase in mortality in Russia and in Azerbaijan also noted from diseases of the blood circulatory system (11,6 and 26,2%), respiratory organs (63,1 and 68,4%). In Azerbaijan, the death rate due to COVID-19 is included in mortality due to infectious diseases. The share of mortality due to COVID-19 in the structure of all causes of mortality in Russia was 6,8%, and in Azerbaijan 6,6%. Based on the World Mortality Database [12], it was shown that the estimated excess number of deaths in Azerbaijan were 53,500. At the same time, the estimated excess mortality rate was 2,71‰. For Russia, this indicator was 3,74‰ [12]. In Azerbaijan, the difference between the number of deaths during the years of the pandemic and before the pandemic was 39357, the data [12] is significantly overestimated. The increase in mortality in Russia in 2020 was 2,35‰ [19], not 3,71‰ [12].

In Russia [20], for the period 2019-2020, the increase in mortality from all causes was 2,35‰ (in Azerbaijan 1,94‰), including 0,676‰ from diseases of the circulatory system (in Azerbaijan 0,853‰), 0,256‰ from the respiratory organs (in Azerbaijan 0,128‰). The low level of increase in mortality for 2020 in Azerbaijan is associated with the age composition of the population. When standardized by age, the increase in all-cause mortality in Azerbaijan in 2020 (2,76‰) exceeds the corresponding value in Russia (2,35‰). The increase in the standardized mortality rate for 2020 and 2021 (compared to 2019) was 1,31‰ and 2,25‰ in Moscow, 1,57‰ and 2,76‰ in St. Petersburg [2]. In Azerbaijan, these indicators are relatively high (2,70 and 3,09‰).

A distinctive feature of the death rate of the population during the pandemic period in Azerbaijan is the lack of an increase in mortality from diseases of the digestive system (table). In Russia [6] in 2020, mortality from diseases of the digestive system increased by more than 8,9%.

Symptoms, signs and ill-defined conditions were reported as causes of death in Moscow [3] in 4,7% of cases before the pandemic and 5,5% of cases during the pandemic. According to our data, in Azerbaijan, the share of reported conditions among all causes of death was 2,8% before the pandemic and 5,4% during the pandemic.

Thus, excessive mortality of the population of Azerbaijan during the COVID-19 pandemic has significant features due to the medical-social and medical-organizational situation in the country.

CONCLUSION

1. In Azerbaijan, before the COVID-19 pandemic, the annual mortality rate of the population was 5,7‰ (standardized level 8,5‰), the main causes of mortality were diseases of the circulatory system (3,361‰), neoplasms (0,888‰), external influences (0,281‰), diseases of the digestive system (0,268‰).

2. During the pandemic, mortality has increased from 5,7‰ to 7,65‰ (excessive mortality of 1,95‰) mainly due to excessive mortality from infectious (COVID-19) diseases (0,554‰), diseases of the blood circulatory system (0,776‰), diseases of the respiratory system (0,176‰), external influences (0,17‰), neoplasms (0,095‰), diseases of the nervous system (0,077‰) and symptoms, syndromes and ill-defined conditions (0,12‰).

3. After the pandemic, the average annual mortality rate (5,95‰) remained high compared to the pre-pandemic period, the excess mortality was 0,25‰ (0,221‰ symptoms, syndromes and ill-defined conditions ill-defined conditions; 0,0605‰ infectious diseases; 0,0195 ‰ external influences; 0,01‰ neoplasms).

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